

The Relationship between the Social Investment and Volume of Freight Carried by Water Transport in Vietnam

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 21 July 2022	This article explored the relationship between social investment and volume of freight carried by water transport in Vietnam during the period 2002 Q4 to 2022 Q2. Using a VAR approach we capture their relationship. The findings suggest an overall, substantial investment has the potential to promote Volume of freight in Vietnam. We recommend more investments towards water transport infrastructure to ensure a significant increase in trade, and to enhance Vietnam's trade competitiveness.
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KEYWORDS: Social investment; volume of freight; water transport; VAR model	

1. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Vietnam's economy had many positive changes after the economic reform in 1986, continued to grow after joining the World Trade Organization WTO in 2007. This result is a clear signal shows the effectiveness of the economic transformation and policies that Vietnam has been implementing, especially in the current globalized environment. From 2002 to 2020 GDP per capita increased 3.6 times reaching nearly 3,700 USD (Worldbank, 2022).

The development of the economy would not be possible without adequate development of transport. Freight transport is an essential and integral part of the national development planning process because it promotes the full exploitation of factors of production. According to the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), maritime remains the backbone of global trade and manufacturing supply chains. (UNCTAD, 2020) reports that more than a quarter of world trade volume is conducted through seaway. Furthermore, ocean freight handles 80% of trade by volume at about 70% of its value (UNCTAD 2020). According to the UNCTAD 2019 report, this trade has linked the global economy and plays an important role in promoting trade and social development. This is also true for the growth of Vietnam, a country that is not least dependent on an extensive transport system, including the water transport system.

Maritime shipping not only faces rapid growth in demand and pressure from shipping services, but also technical challenges including outdated infrastructure leading to congestion and delays. Furthermore, this includes a lack of investment to upgrade and maintain port infrastructure. (W.

Matekenya, 2022). According to data from the Asian Development Bank, infrastructure investment in both the public and private sector of Vietnam is reaching about 5.7% of GDP in recent years, the highest in Southeast Asia and ranked second in Asia after China (Minh, n.d.). Investment capital for development is increasing but still does not meet the demand, posing a big task is to increase the mobilization and use of investment capital effectively.

1.1 Overview of water transport in Vietnam

Water transport includes maritime and inland waterway transport. Both perform freight as well as passenger transport. (Coyle, Novack, & Gibson, 2016). Volume of freight carried is the volume of cargoes transported by transportation establishments and others operating in transportation business activities regardless of travel distance. Volume of freight carried is calculated by the actual weight of goods carried (including packing). It is only measured after the completion of transportation to the destination as mentioned in the contracts and finishing delivery procedure. Volume of freight traffic is volume of freight traffic through a length of transportation distance, that is calculated by multiplying volume of freight carried with the actual transported distance.

Figure 1 represents the freight transport volume and activities of the different modes of transport in Viet Nam from 1995 to 2020. Based on statistics obtained from the General Statistics Office of Viet Nam, Vietnam's freight transport market is largely dominated by two modes: Water and road transport. Together, these modes account for 97% of the tons transported annually.

Figure 1. Volume of freight carried by types of transport
Source: GSO

However, the market share of water transport decreased from 32% in 1995 to 20% in 2020 in which the market share of inland waterways decreased significantly from 26.8% to 15%, while the market share of road transport increased from 64.8% to 80.3% over the past several years. Inland waterways transport has been losing tonnage share is from a combination of factors. While inland water transport is low cost and has a larger capacity and flexible service, the speed of transport is very slow, making it unsuitable for transactions where time is an important factor. In addition,

inland water transport is sometimes unreliable as it can only be used when the water level is sufficient, or economic (and population) growth in areas outside the geographic coverage of the waterway transport network, plummeting truck transport rates in an environment of deregulated competition and low barriers to entry, and a significant expansion of the road network (Blancas & El-Hifnawi, 2014). Despite having lost share to the road sector over a number of years, the water transport sector remains essential to the functioning of the Vietnam trade.

Figure 2. Modal shares (based on tons)
Source: GSO

Although maritime shipping carries a tonnage share that at 5% is lower than IWT, Official statistics from the GSO show that, between 1995 and 2020, maritime shipping tonnage grew at a rate of 8.5 —faster than IWT tonnage rate of 5.5% but still slower than road tonnage.

Table 1 shows the 2008 modal shares of freight transportation by commodity. The inland water transport in Viet Nam is mainly used for transport of large bulk commodities mainly construction materials, cement, coal and agricultural products. Coastal shipping had an advantage for

long-distance trips for products such as cement, coal, and manufacturing goods.

Table 1. Modal shares of freight transportation by commodity

Commodity	IWT	Coastal	Road	Rail	Total	% IWT	% Coastal
Rice	36,109	4,261	78,969	204	119,543	30	4
Sugar cane/sugar	4,847	88	3,682	0	8,617	56	1
Wood	11,683	914	11,499	523	24,619	47	4
Steel	1,015	764	41,965	2,156	45,900	2	2
Construction materials	370,787	1,914	129,219	8,213	510,133	73	0
Cement	64,387	13,021	38,965	3,810	120,183	54	11
Fertilizer	28,678	1,168	8,813	2,939	41,598	69	3
Coal	92,549	10,092	12,106	2,377	117,124	79	9
Petroleum	5,018	8,234	33,374	404	47,030	11	18
Industrial crops	2,415	0	5,628	0	8,043	30	0
Manufacturing goods	3,916	13,524	171,895	4,895	194,481	2	7
Fishery products	12,203	0	7,186	0	19,389	63	0
Animal meat and others	9,373	4,118	61,578	0	75,069	12	5
Total (tons/day)	642,980	58,098	604,879	25,521	1,331,729	n.a.	n.a.

Source: (Blancas & El-Hifnawi, 2014)

1.2 Overview of total social investment In vietnam

Social investment is the entire amount of capital spending (expenditure) to increase or maintain capacity and resources for production, including: investment to generate fixed assets, investment to increase current assets, spending on purchasing rare and precious assets, reserves gold in the form of goods, storage of commodities in the resident and other investment to improve people’s knowledge, enhance social welfare, improve the ecological environment, support people’s welfare, etc. The nature of total investment for social development includes investment from the public sector, private sector, and foreign direct investment.

Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the investment by types of ownership in Vietnam from 1995 to 2022. Over the last 25 years, Vietnam investment has increased significantly. This increase shows a positive signal in mobilizing and using social investment for socio-economic development. This is also an important driving force contributing to economic growth. In the period 1995 - 2017, the largest share of total investment came from the public sector, but in the period after 2018 the proportion came from the private sector.

Figure 3. Investment by types of ownership in Vietnam from 1995-2020
Source: GSO

Figure 4. Investment by types of ownership in Vietnam from 2018-2022

Source: GSO

In 10 years from 1996 to 2005, transport sector has renovated, upgraded and renewed more than 16,000 km of roads; 1,400 km of railway; more than 130,000 md of road bridges; 11,000 m long railway bridge, upgrading and building a new 5,400 m long harbor; dredging 4.8 million m3 of canals. (MT, 2014)

Regarding the island way, two southern waterways have been upgraded (Hochiminh City - Ca Mau, Hochiminh City - Kien Luong); and step by step upgrade other major river routes. Regarding maritime, the Transport Industry in the past period has completed the first phase of upgrading major national seaports such as Cai Lan Port, Hai Phong Port, Cua Lo Port, Vung Ang Port, Tien Sa Port, and so on. Quy Nhon Port, Nha Trang Port, Saigon Port, Can Tho Port and complete the upgrading of a number of local ports necessary to meet the throughput of goods (MT, 2014)

With more than 3,200 km of coastline, Viet Nam currently has 37 seaports, with 166 docks and 350 wharfs, with a total length of about 45,000 m of wharves and capacity of about 350-370 million-tons per year. Port groups have been established and are capable of receiving vessels with the load of up to 100,000 tons in containers. The construction of international gateway ports in key economic zones and wharves in other areas is ongoing. (CleanAirAsia, ICCT, & CCAC, 2017)

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

(Munim & Schramm, 2018) conducted an empirical investigation for 91 developed and developing countries. Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used to provide empirical evidence on the significant economic impacts of port infrastructure quality and logistics performance. The results show that it is important for developing countries to continuously improve the quality of port infrastructure resulting in higher seaborne trade. However, this impact weakens as developing countries become richer.

(T.R.Lakshmanan, 2011) highlight the benefits of transport infrastructure from the observed role of railroads

and waterways in economic growth and identify the mechanisms which connect transport and economic growth. Investment is an exogenous factor that plays an important role in the quality of port infrastructure by improving it. Thus, better infrastructure will improve the logistics efficiency of the country's trade and will expand the market by providing opportunities for both local and international market.

(AlbertoPortugal-Perez, 2012) estimate the impact of aggregate indicators of “soft” and “hard” infrastructure on the export performance of more than 100 countries over the period 2004–07. The research shows that investments in infrastructure create a better business environment and transport efficiency, which improve export growth.

(Song & Geenuhuizenc, 2014) estimate the output elasticity of port infrastructure in China applying panel data analysis for the period of 1999–2010. The results indicate clear positive effects of port infrastructure investment in all regions, however, the strength varies considerably among the regions.

(Sakyi & Immurana, 2021) show empirical evidence on the effect of seaport efficiency on the trade balance in a sample of 27 African countries for the period 2010-2017 by using Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) estimation technique. From a policy-oriented perspective, improving the efficiency of seaports in Africa is the goal of policy reforms.

In the Vietnam context to date, there is not much research indicating the impact of investment on volume of freight. This study attempts to contribute towards exploring the the relationship between the investment capital and volume of freight carried by water transport in vietnam and also contributing to the body of literature on the subject.

3. METHODOLOGY AND RESULT

3.1 Methodology

To carry out the topic, qualitative research is conducted on theoretical documents and previous researches in order to build the research model, and then apply quantitative research on research model. To evaluate the

relationship between investment and the volume of goods transported by waterway in Vietnam, three variables are used in the analytical model: the total social investment capital (*tiv*), Volume of freight carried in tons (*vfc*) and volume of freight traffic in ton.km (*vft*). Due to data limitations, the research utilized quarterly data about the country of Vietnam in the period 2002-2022 from the Vietnam General Statistics Office.

After collecting data, the study uses EViews to perform analysis such as descriptive statistics and regression. To evaluate the relationship between investment and the volume of goods transported by waterway in Vietnam, this study uses the VAR model. The research model is estimated by the least squares method considering the correlation and

stationarity when using time series data. The process is carried out as follows: first the stationarity test, next choose the optimal lag which is the lag at which the variables modeled over the lagged variable and other variables with the same lag give the best results. The determination of the optimal lag is based on the selection index . Then cointegration test, model fit test, Granger causality test, then push response function analysis and finally variance decomposition analysis (Agung, 2009).

3.2 The results

The Unit root test confirm that the data of these variables are non-stationary and therefore to process these time series, the first difference for analysis is taken.

Table 2. Unit root test

Variable	ADF test	t - statistics		
		1%	5%	10%
DTIV	-3.2 (0.0259)	-3.523	-2.902	-2.588
DVFC	-4.3 (0.0009)	-3.527	-2.903	-2.589
DVFT	-5.0 (0.0001)	-3.525	-2.903	-2.589

Source: Authors’ own calculation

According to the results of literature review, it shows that time series economic variables usually have a certain lag when considering the impact between variables. The results of the analysis are shown in Table 3. According

to the test criteria, determined by the AIC and HQ criteria, we can determine the optimal delay length, the optimal delay of the model for DTIV and DVFC is 4 and for DTIV and DVFT is 2.

Table 3. VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria for DTIV and DVFC

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-1057.147	NA	1.84e+11	31.61632	31.68213*	31.64236
1	-1051.189	11.38153	1.74e+11	31.55788	31.75532	31.63601
2	-1042.486	16.10671	1.51e+11	31.41750	31.74656	31.54771
3	-1041.636	1.523715	1.66e+11	31.51151	31.97219	31.69380
4	-1029.562	20.90278*	1.31e+11*	31.27052*	31.86283	31.50490*
5	-1027.902	2.775764	1.41e+11	31.34036	32.06428	31.62682
6	-1026.120	2.872643	1.51e+11	31.40656	32.26211	31.74511
7	-1024.406	2.659997	1.63e+11	31.47481	32.46199	31.86544
8	-1019.777	6.908555	1.61e+11	31.45604	32.57484	31.89875

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion
 LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)
 FPE: Final prediction error
 AIC: Akaike information criterion
 SC: Schwarz information criterion
 HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

Source: Authors’ own calculation

To ensure the conclusions from the estimated model, the authors test the violation of the assumptions of the regression estimate. The stability test shows that all the roots

is inside the unit circle, which indicates that the VAR model is stable, as shown in Figure 5. Therefore, this model is a good VAR model.

Figure 5. Test of stability

Source: Authors’ own calculation

The results of residual autocorrelation test shown in Table 4 based on statistics show that with different lag steps, the p-values of the statistic are all greater than 5%, that is, the

hypothesis H_0 - No autocorrelation is accepted and the model is considered to satisfy the condition that there is no autocorrelation of residuals.

Table 4. VAR Residual Serial Correlation LM Tests

Lag	LRE* stat df	Prob.	Rao F-statdf	Prob.
1	3.819502 4	0.4310	0.962211 (4, 118.0)	0.4310
2	1.246013 4	0.8705	0.310508 (4, 118.0)	0.8705
3	0.305963 4	0.9894	0.075946 (4, 118.0)	0.9894
4	5.158834 4	0.2714	1.306996 (4, 118.0)	0.2714
5	0.515129 4	0.9720	0.127977 (4, 118.0)	0.9720

Source: Authors’ own calculation

Thus, the VAR model to assess the relationship between social investment and volume of freight in Vietnam is appropriate and stable, the conclusions from the estimation

results are reliable. Next, Granger causality is conducted with the results shown in Table 5 below.

Table 5. Check Granger causes–effects

H_0	chi-sq	p- value	Conclusion
DTIV does not Granger Cause DVFC	10.06301	0.0394	Volume freight carried in tons depends on the social investment
DVFC does not Granger Cause DTIV	2.776825	0.5958	Social investment does not depend on the Volume freight carried in tons
DTIV does not Granger Cause DVFT	2.545596	0.2800	Volume freight traffic in tons.km does not depends on the social investment
DVFT does not Granger Cause DTIV	1.290353	0.5246	Social investment does not depend on the Volume freight traffic in tons.km

Source: Authors’ own calculation

Figure 6 and Table 6 displays the results of impulse Response and variance decomposition of DVFC for 20 periods/.

Response to Cholesky One S.D. (d.f. adjusted) Innovations ± 2 S.E.

Figure 6. Impulse Response

Source: Authors’ own calculation

Table 6. The results of variance decomposition of DVFC

Period	S.E.	DTIV	DVFC
1	7304.898	0.148446	99.85155
2	7636.201	0.418015	99.58199
3	7949.576	6.150303	93.84970
4	7950.442	6.154576	93.84542
5	9455.362	11.51006	88.48994
6	9983.280	13.92493	86.07507
7	10793.27	24.58900	75.41100
8	10946.37	26.54365	73.45635
9	11389.17	24.65945	75.34055
10	11727.32	23.90845	76.09155
11	12219.92	27.44351	72.55649
12	12392.07	28.90255	71.09745
13	12542.20	28.27235	71.72765
14	12758.99	27.49632	72.50368
15	13108.81	28.79508	71.20492
16	13302.00	29.91885	70.08115
17	13359.98	30.02451	69.97549
18	13478.61	29.50354	70.49646
19	13715.13	29.77867	70.22133
20	13903.79	30.49849	69.50151

Source: Authors’ own calculation

Based on the results of the push reaction analysis and the decomposition of variance, the variation in volume is correlated with investment and its past values. However, it is until the third quarter that investment has a clearly impact on volume and tends to increase over time. After 11 periods - 3 years, the impact of investment on volume does not change much. Thus, besides promoting investment for social, the government also needs other policies to increase the volume of freight.

4. CONCLUSION

The purpose of the research was to examine the relationship between social investment and volume of freight carried by water transport in Vietnam, the VAR technique was employed and shown that social investment has a positive

impact on volume of freight, thus indicating the importance of investment in this sector.

Based on the results, it is recommend that Vietnam continued investment for enhancing the capacity and commercial development of the country. To be able to take advantage of the opportunities and benefits of the existing water transport system and increase the volume of freight, continuous improvement and maintenance of the water infrastructure is required. This has the potential to boost the country's economic development and trade turnover.

5. LIMITATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The main limitation of this study is data availability. The available data for investment only covers quarterly data for the period 2002 to 2022. To explore other analysis, future research would also look at the impact of investment on

economic growth or the impact of investment and other policies of government on trade of Vietnam.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1. Unit root test

Null Hypothesis: DTIV has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant

Lag Length: 1 (Automatic - based on AIC, maxlag=16)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-3.169713	0.0259
Test critical values: 1% level	-3.522887	
5% level	-2.901779	
10% level	-2.588280	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(DTIV)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 07/14/22 Time: 21:08
 Sample (adjusted): 2004Q2 2022Q2
 Included observations: 73 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
DTIV(-1)	-0.411070	0.129687	-3.169713	0.0023
D(DTIV(-1))	-0.419604	0.108883	-3.853723	0.0003
C	16.22358	6.960576	2.330781	0.0227
R-squared	0.465981	Mean dependent var		0.789667
Adjusted R-squared	0.450723	S.D. dependent var		58.04235
S.E. of regression	43.01704	Akaike info criterion		10.40130
Sum squared resid	129532.6	Schwarz criterion		10.49543
Log likelihood	-376.6473	Hannan-Quinn criter.		10.43881
F-statistic	30.54076	Durbin-Watson stat		1.956609
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Null Hypothesis: DVFC has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant
 Lag Length: 4 (Automatic - based on AIC, maxlag=16)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-4.329541	0.0009
Test critical values: 1% level	-3.527045	
5% level	-2.903566	
10% level	-2.589227	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation
 Dependent Variable: D(DVFC)
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 07/14/22 Time: 21:09
 Sample (adjusted): 2005Q1 2022Q2
 Included observations: 70 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
DVFC(-1)	-1.059916	0.244810	-4.329541	0.0001
D(DVFC(-1))	0.393561	0.193212	2.036936	0.0458
D(DVFC(-2))	0.381265	0.180328	2.114285	0.0384
D(DVFC(-3))	0.324086	0.165928	1.953172	0.0552
D(DVFC(-4))	-0.187671	0.147445	-1.272817	0.2077
C	5396.955	1521.885	3.546230	0.0007
R-squared	0.485444	Mean dependent var		148.6261
Adjusted R-squared	0.445244	S.D. dependent var		10263.85
S.E. of regression	7644.716	Akaike info criterion		20.80323

Sum squared resid	3.74E+09	Schwarz criterion	20.99596
Log likelihood	-722.1132	Hannan-Quinn criter.	20.87979
F-statistic	12.07580	Durbin-Watson stat	2.011788
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Null Hypothesis: DVFT has a unit root

Exogenous: Constant

Lag Length: 3 (Automatic - based on AIC, maxlag=16)

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-5.024161	0.0001
Test critical values: 1% level	-3.525618	
5% level	-2.902953	
10% level	-2.588902	

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation

Dependent Variable: D(DVFT)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 07/14/22 Time: 21:09

Sample (adjusted): 2004Q4 2022Q2

Included observations: 71 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
DVFT(-1)	-0.768957	0.153052	-5.024161	0.0000
D(DVFT(-1))	0.055477	0.153149	0.362240	0.7183
D(DVFT(-2))	0.337691	0.144698	2.333773	0.0227
D(DVFT(-3))	0.497404	0.114209	4.355217	0.0000
C	2492.403	891.0268	2.797226	0.0067
R-squared	0.504830	Mean dependent var	231.1974	
Adjusted R-squared	0.474819	S.D. dependent var	9059.953	
S.E. of regression	6565.689	Akaike info criterion	20.48492	
Sum squared resid	2.85E+09	Schwarz criterion	20.64427	
Log likelihood	-722.2147	Hannan-Quinn criter.	20.54829	
F-statistic	16.82187	Durbin-Watson stat	1.784009	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Appendix 2. VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Endogenous variables: DTIV DVFC

Exogenous variables: C

Date: 07/14/22 Time: 21:10

Sample: 2002Q4 2022Q2

Included observations: 67

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-1057.147	NA	1.84e+11	31.61632	31.68213*	31.64236
1	-1051.189	11.38153	1.74e+11	31.55788	31.75532	31.63601

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2	-1042.486	16.10671	1.51e+11	31.41750	31.74656	31.54771
3	-1041.636	1.523715	1.66e+11	31.51151	31.97219	31.69380
4	-1029.562	20.90278*	1.31e+11*	31.27052*	31.86283	31.50490*
5	-1027.902	2.775764	1.41e+11	31.34036	32.06428	31.62682
6	-1026.120	2.872643	1.51e+11	31.40656	32.26211	31.74511
7	-1024.406	2.659997	1.63e+11	31.47481	32.46199	31.86544
8	-1019.777	6.908555	1.61e+11	31.45604	32.57484	31.89875

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion

LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)

FPE: Final prediction error

AIC: Akaike information criterion

SC: Schwarz information criterion

HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Endogenous variables: DTIV DVFT

Exogenous variables: C

Date: 07/14/22 Time: 21:12

Sample: 2002Q4 2022Q2

Included observations: 67

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-1051.100	NA	1.54e+11	31.43581	31.50162	31.46185
1	-1044.168	13.24213	1.41e+11	31.34831	31.54574	31.42643
2	-1033.978	18.85893	1.17e+11	31.16353	31.49259*	31.29374*
3	-1033.865	0.203880	1.32e+11	31.27954	31.74022	31.46183
4	-1022.695	19.33808*	1.07e+11*	31.06553*	31.65783	31.29990
5	-1021.803	1.491231	1.17e+11	31.15830	31.88223	31.44476
6	-1020.564	1.997136	1.28e+11	31.24072	32.09627	31.57926
7	-1018.309	3.499899	1.36e+11	31.29282	32.27999	31.68344
8	-1015.090	4.805283	1.40e+11	31.31611	32.43491	31.75883

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion

LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)

FPE: Final prediction error

AIC: Akaike information criterion

SC: Schwarz information criterion

HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

Appendix 3. Test of stability

Roots of Characteristic Polynomial

Endogenous variables: DTIV DVFC

Exogenous variables: C

Lag specification: 1 4

Date: 07/14/22 Time: 21:14

Root	Modulus
0.727516 - 0.633225i	0.964496
0.727516 + 0.633225i	0.964496
-0.613355 - 0.626524i	0.876776
-0.613355 + 0.626524i	0.876776
0.609262 - 0.168143i	0.632038
0.609262 + 0.168143i	0.632038

-0.491931 - 0.291993i 0.572063
 -0.491931 + 0.291993i 0.572063

No root lies outside the unit circle.
 VAR satisfies the stability condition.

Roots of Characteristic Polynomial
 Endogenous variables: DTIV DVFT
 Exogenous variables: C
 Lag specification: 1 2
 Date: 07/14/22 Time: 21:13

Root	Modulus
0.731188	0.731188
0.613407	0.613407
-0.458809 - 0.104392i	0.470536
-0.458809 + 0.104392i	0.470536

No root lies outside the unit circle.
 VAR satisfies the stability condition.

Appendix 4. Residual Serial Correlation LM Tests

VAR Residual Serial Correlation LM Tests
 Date: 07/15/22 Time: 15:49
 Sample: 2002Q4 2022Q2
 Included observations: 71

Null hypothesis: No serial correlation at lag h

Lag	LRE* stat	df	Prob.	Rao F-stat	df	Prob.
1	3.819502	4	0.4310	0.962211	(4, 118.0)	0.4310
2	1.246013	4	0.8705	0.310508	(4, 118.0)	0.8705
3	0.305963	4	0.9894	0.075946	(4, 118.0)	0.9894
4	5.158834	4	0.2714	1.306996	(4, 118.0)	0.2714
5	0.515129	4	0.9720	0.127977	(4, 118.0)	0.9720

Null hypothesis: No serial correlation at lags 1 to h

Lag	LRE* stat	df	Prob.	Rao F-stat	df	Prob.
1	3.819502	4	0.4310	0.962211	(4, 118.0)	0.4310
2	4.156796	8	0.8427	0.515377	(8, 114.0)	0.8428
3	5.072297	12	0.9555	0.413363	(12, 110.0)	0.9556
4	11.47974	16	0.7790	0.708413	(16, 106.0)	0.7800
5	13.76622	20	0.8421	0.673397	(20, 102.0)	0.8436

*Edgeworth expansion corrected likelihood ratio statistic.

Appendix 5. IMPULSE RESPONSE

Response to Cholesky One S.D. (d.f. adjusted) Innovations ± 2 S.E.

Appendix 6. Variance Decomposition

Variance Decomposition using Cholesky (d.f. adjusted) Factors

Variance Decomposition of DTIV

Variance Decomposition of DVFC

